

Harmonised European Solutions for Testing Automation Road Transport

HEADSTART D6.2. Dissemination and Communication Strategy

Work package	WP6: Communication and Dissemination
Task	Task 6.2: Dissemination and Communication Strategy
Deliverable Lead	ICCS
Authors	Nikoletta Karitsioti (ICCS), Kelly Panagiotidi (ICCS), Álvaro Arrúe (IDIADA), Julie Castermans (ERTICO), Floriane Schreiner (VEDECOM), Oihana Otaegui (VICOMTECH)
Dissemination level	Public (PU)
Status	Draft
Due date	30/06/2019
Document date	27/05/2020
Version number	1.0

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 824309.

PARTNERS

Disclaimer:

Content reflects only the authors’ view and European Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

Revision and history chart

Version	Date	Main author	Summary of changes
0.1	25/05/2019	Nikoletta Karitsioti	Draft outline for input
0.2	15/06/2019	Nikoletta Karitsioti	Integration of comments and input received by Álvaro Arrúe (IDIADA)
0.3	18/06/2019	Nikoletta Karitsioti	Integration of comments and input received from Julie Castermans (ERTICO)
0.4	19/06/2019	Nikoletta Karitsioti	Integration of comments from VEDECOM
0.5	21/06/2019	Nikoletta Karitsioti	New draft outline for review from IDIADA and ERTICO partners
0.6	01/07/2019	Julie Castermans	Review from ERTICO
0.7	01/07/2019	Nikoletta Karitsioti	Integration of comments from ERTICO
0.8	04/07/2019	Álvaro Arrúe	Review from IDIADA
1.0	08/07/2019	Nikoletta Karitsioti	Final submitted version

Table of contents

List of abbreviations and acronyms	viii
Executive Summary	1
1 Introduction	1
1.1 Aim of the project.....	1
1.2 Purpose and scope.....	2
1.2.1 Intended Readership	2
1.2.2 Interface with other HEADSTART deliverables	2
2 Dissemination and Communication Strategy	2
2.1 The definitions	2
2.2 The strategy	4
2.3 Dissemination and Communication Goals.....	6
2.4 Audiences and approach	6
2.4.1 Target Audiences	6
2.4.2 Key messages per target audience	9
3 Liaison and Networking activities	10
4 Key communication and dissemination tools & channels.....	11
4.1 Online communication and dissemination tools & channels	13
4.1.1 Website.....	13
4.1.2 HEADSTART Social Media	15
4.1.3 Hashtags	20
4.1.4 Online newsletter	21
4.2 Offline communication and dissemination tools & channels.....	22
4.2.1 Brand Identity.....	22
4.2.2 HEADSTART Logo	22
4.2.3 Project Templates.....	22
4.2.4 Printed Material.....	22
4.2.5 Press Activities	23
4.2.6 Scientific publications	25
5 Key communication activities	25
5.1 Expert’s Workshops	25
5.2 Demonstrations	26

6	Dissemination Roadmap.....	26
6.1	1 st year Dissemination Activities.....	27
6.2	2 nd year Dissemination Activities.....	27
6.3	3 rd year Dissemination Activities.....	27
6.4	After the project’s end Dissemination Activities.....	28
7	Events.....	28
7.1	HEADSTART Project Events.....	28
7.1.1	Stakeholders’ Workshop.....	28
7.1.2	Final Event.....	28
7.2	External Events.....	28
8	Dissemination Procedures – Partner’s Roles.....	30
8.1	Dissemination Procedures.....	30
8.2	Dissemination records.....	32
8.3	Partner’s Roles.....	32
8.3.1	WP6 Responsibilities.....	32
8.3.2	Communication and Dissemination Manager.....	33
8.3.3	HEADSTART Dissemination Group.....	33
8.3.4	HEADSTART project event organizing committees.....	33
8.3.5	All partners.....	34
8.3.6	Timing of official WP6 Deliverables.....	34
9	Conclusions.....	37
10	References.....	38
	Annex 1: Communication and dissemination material.....	39
	HEADSTART Brand identity.....	39
	HEADSTART Templates.....	46
	PPT template (indicative slides).....	46
	Deliverable template (cover page).....	48
	Minutes template.....	48
	Press Activities.....	51
	HEADSTART Communication kit.....	54
	General Presentation.....	54
	Annex 2: Dissemination procedures.....	62
	HEADSTART Dissemination Activities Report.....	65

Report on Non-European Travel.....	70
Annex 3: HEADSTART indicative list of proposed events.....	71

Index of figures

Figure 1, the laswell model of communication	4
Figure 2, communication and dissemination concept per year	5
Figure 3, the headstart website's homepage	14
Figure 4, headstart twitter account.....	17
Figure 5, headstart group on linkedin	18
Figure 6, headstart page on linkedin	19
Figure 7, headstart page on facebook	20
Figure 8, headstart responsive hashtags	21
Figure 9, the headstart logo	22

Index of tables

Table 1, excerpt from ec guidance for the social media guide for eu funded R&I projects	3
Table 2, the laswell five models.....	4
Table 3, headstart target audiences	7
Table 4, headstart key messages per target audience	9
Table 5, number of liaison activities per year as identified in the ga	11
Table 6, communication and dissemination tools and channels per audience	11
Table 7, number of visitors and page-views per year.....	13
Table 8, number of social media campaigns as is identified in ga	16
Table 9, number of followers in twitter account	16
Table 10, headstart linkedin followers as identified in ga	17
Table 11, number of e-newsletter recipients per year as has been identified in ga	21
Table 12, news articles	24
Table 13, journal articles per year	25
Table 14, number of special sessions per year	29
Table 15, headstart participation in events & conferences.....	29
Table 16, participation per partner	32
Table 17, wp6 deliverables	35

List of abbreviations and acronyms

Abbreviation	Meaning
CAD	Connected and Automated Driving
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
PO	Project Officer
WP	Work Package

Executive Summary

The D6.2 Dissemination and Communication Strategy is carried out as part of HEADSTART WP6 Communication and Dissemination, specifically Task 6.1 Dissemination and Communication Strategy.

The HEADSTART Dissemination and Communication Strategy aims to describe the project's overall dissemination and communication strategy, identifies the target audiences, provides the key messages at target-group specific levels, presents the online and offline dissemination and communication tools and channels as well as the dissemination roadmap, the partners' contribution and the dissemination procedures to be followed.

The purpose of this Dissemination and Communication Strategy is to provide a guide for the HEADSTART consortium for efficiently allocating time and resources, create awareness, engage with relevant stakeholders and also disseminate the project's activities, outcomes and results while striving for maximum impact.

In its first chapter, the reader has the opportunity to find out initial information about the project as well as the purpose of this Deliverable. In the second chapter, is detailed the Dissemination and Communication Strategy to be followed within the lifetime of the project, taking into consideration the project's objectives. The target audiences are identified while specific key messages per target audience are established.

In the third chapter, is presented the effort that HEADSTART partners will make in order to develop liaisons with other projects and initiatives related to HEADSTART's concept. Following, the reader is able to find out the key communication channels and tools, online and offline, that will be used within the project's lifetime as well as the key communication activities and events that will take place. Moreover, the Dissemination Roadmap to be followed per year is thoroughly presented as well as the events – internal and external – where the project will be disseminated.

Last but not least, the Dissemination Procedures to be followed are described so as to secure the effective dissemination of the project, while the partners' responsibilities in WP6 and its specific activities will be recorded accordingly. The report also includes a set of annexes, including: Annex 1: Communication and dissemination material, Annex 2: Dissemination procedures and Annex 3: HEADSTART indicative list of proposed events.

This Deliverable is a live document which will be updated in the course of the project. While at the early stages of the project the communication and dissemination is more concentrated on presentations of the idea and concept of the work to be deployed, at later stages the communication and dissemination task will focus on presenting the achieved developments and results. Thus, this deliverable on its updates (D6.3 and D6.4), on M19 and M36, will be enriched with a list of activities in which HEADSTART took part, reports on the efficiency of the different communication and dissemination channels and tools taking into consideration the defined KPIs, website's statistics as well as with results coming from the events and activities that took place.

1 Introduction

1.1 Aim of the project

The Connected and Automated Mobility is expected to be an essential component in the pursuit of a safer, cleaner, more efficient and more user-friendly mobility system. For this, EU Member States, industry as well as the European Commission collaborate to achieve the ambitious vision of European Union, taking into consideration public authorities, citizens, cities and industry interests. The introduction and deployment of Connected and Automated Mobility is supported by the European Commission on various levels, such as policy

initiatives, policy strategies in collaboration with industries, standards' development, research and innovation projects, etc.

In this context, the main motivation of HEADSTART is the assurance of safety in Connected and Automated Driving. More specifically, HEADSTART, aims to define testing and validation procedures of Connected and Automated Driving functions including key technologies such as communications, cyber-security and positioning. HEADSTART will launch the tests in both simulation and real-world fields to validate safety and security performance according to the key users' needs. Its ultimate aim is to bring together the consortium with other European and national CAD stakeholders to cluster the most relevant existing initiatives, develop methodologies, procedures and tools and drive in a harmonized European solution for testing and validation of automated road vehicles.

HEADSTART will identify and harmonise the existing methodologies, procedures and tools and also define and develop test, validation and certification methodologies for CAD functions. In addition, will demonstrate the developed methodologies, procedures and tools through testing 4 CAD use cases and reach consensus by creating and managing an expert network to promote adoption of the project results.

1.2 Purpose and scope

The current deliverable, named as D6.2 Communication and Dissemination Strategy consists in a key reference document for all the procedures and activities to be implemented within WP6, Communication and Dissemination, of HEADSTART project. It is intended as a live document through the project's lifetime and it is subject to periodical updates (D6.3, M18 & D6.4, M36).

The purpose of this document is to provide an initial, detailed and carefully-designed communication and dissemination strategy and plan for the activities to be performed within HEADSTART project. The presented set of processes will remain active throughout the project's lifetime to effectively help the consortium to achieve the desired outreach to relevant audiences and disseminate the project's achievements in the targeted audiences. In order to keep the alignment of the communication and dissemination strategy with the findings and results of the project, this deliverable will be revised and new deliverables will follow in M18 (D6.3) and M36 (D6.4).

1.2.1 Intended Readership

This deliverable is public (PU dissemination level) and therefore is intended for consortium partners, including the European Commission services, as well as individuals who are interested in getting more information about the HEADSTART project.

1.2.2 Interface with other HEADSTART deliverables

This deliverable lies within WP6, Communication and Dissemination Strategy and is considered as the 'foundation' document of WP6, as it includes the whole strategy to be followed within the course of the project. This deliverable will be consequently updated according to project's needs. It is strongly related to the D6.1 Website, as the website is one of the project's main communications and dissemination tools.

2 Dissemination and Communication Strategy

2.1 The definitions

Communication refers to the project promotion, and its themes and the challenges which will be encountered. Consortium partners must undertake all means at their disposal to efficiently promote the action and its results, by spreading targeted information to multiple audiences (including the media and the public), in a strategic and effective way in order to achieve a two-way exchange. A comprehensive communication plan should include a clear definition of its objectives, define key messages tailored to each target audience and set out an accurate

roadmap of activities. This process will more effectively promote the creation of communication strategies that can be adopted more easily for any situation.

TABLE 1, EXCERPT FROM EC GUIDANCE FOR THE SOCIAL MEDIA GUIDE FOR EU FUNDED R&I PROJECTS

Communication	Dissemination
Covers the whole project (including results)	Covers project results only
Starts at the outset of the project	Happens only once results are available
Multiple audiences Beyond the project's own community, including the media and general public. Multiplier effect.	Specialist audiences Groups that may use the results in their own work, including peer groups, industry, professional organisations, policymakers
Informing and engaging with society, to show how it can benefit from research	Enabling the take-up and use of results
Legal reference: Grant Agreement Article 38.1	Legal reference: Grant Agreement Article 29

Dissemination is a process utilized to enhance the impact, visibility and credibility of a project. It refers to the public disclosure of the results of the project by appropriate means. Dissemination may be achieved by sharing information concerning the project and the publication of the project’s findings using traditional media channels (newsletters, publications, news media coverage), and digital media (social media). Dissemination may also be achieved through the publications from projects in peer-reviewed scientific journals, presentations in scientific conferences and in industry related events.

Communication and dissemination can be considered as the different sides of the same coin. The boundaries between some of their activities are often blurry and sometimes can create confusion. More specifically, certain tools and activities (e.g. a magazine article that is published for communication purposes can trigger the interest of potential stakeholders in using the presented project outcomes and thus it has automatically become a dissemination tool) can oscillate between communication and dissemination, depending on the target audience and content¹. Thus, what differentiates them are the objectives they have, their main point of focus, and the

¹ EU Grants: H2020 Guidance – Social media guide for EU funded R&I projects: v1.0 – 06.04.2018

target audiences addressed. In this sub-chapter, a clarification on the terminology as well as a clear distinction of their corresponding activities is given, by shedding light on their differences.

According to the recent (2018) EC Guidance for the Social media guide for EU funded R&I projects, both communication and dissemination processes are mandatory and vital for H2020 projects. It is also important that results remain protected at all times. Their differences are presented in the following Table 1.

2.2 The strategy

The communication and dissemination activities require time and financial resources by the consortium partners. It is therefore essential to establish a concise strategy with a predetermined scope and carefully defined goals. This strategy has been designed and will be followed as closely as possible during the project's course.

FIGURE 1, THE LASWELL MODEL OF COMMUNICATION

The HEADSTART communication and dissemination strategy will be based on Laswell model (Figure 1) of five levels of communication (Table 2), (who - Source, what - Message, in which channel or through which medium, to whom – the audience, and to what effect) and is developed in accordance with the European Commission's recommendations on Communication/ Dissemination.

TABLE 2, THE LASWELL FIVE MODELS

Question	Element	Analysis (Outcome)
Who?	Communicator	Control Analysis
Says What?	Message	Content Analysis

Question	Element	Analysis (Outcome)
In Which Channel?	Medium	Media Analysis
To Whom?	Audience	Audience Analysis
With What Effect?	Effect	Effects Analysis

The communication and dissemination strategy includes the definition of communication goals, target groups, communication channels and material per project phase. This means that for each project phase there is a clear plan of cost-efficient communication means, so as to reach the specified target groups through the defined communication channels with the purpose of achieving the communication goals.

The following figure (Figure 2) graphically depicts the project’s communication and dissemination strategy, including an initial planning of the project’s evolution and the rationale to be followed as well as providing all the available means to communicate the project and disseminate its results.

FIGURE 2, COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION CONCEPT PER YEAR

The content of the communication material depends on the project development stage. The communication material reaches the defined target groups through specific communication & dissemination channels which may also vary depending on the project progress. The ultimate goal is to have a sustainable impact also through the public’s increase of awareness of the HEADSTART mandate.

In the initial phase of the project, an emphasis is given on the communication activities, in order to raise awareness and provide general information to the targeted audiences. For this scope, are identified the key messages per target audience. During this phase activities are taking place such as the brand identity design, the

website development, the social media set-up, as well as publication of press releases or media articles in order to boost the project's awareness.

In the second year, within the development phase, extra effort is given towards the communication and dissemination of the project's work. Initial results and findings are promoted so as to attract interest and collect the required feedback, as well as to raise awareness on the project's real developments. During this phase, activities are taking place such as publications in conference proceedings and scientific journals, presentations of projects results in conferences and other events, as well as the organization of internal events, such as workshops, in order to involve interested parties, present the project's initial findings and collect their feedback on this. Furthermore, during this period a first update of the communication kit will take place as well as updates on the website and social media in order to support the project's evolution.

Last but not least, in the final phase of the project, a major effort will be made in effectively disseminating the final project's results to the target audiences. Within this phase, updates in the website and social media will take place, as well as in the communication kit. In addition, media articles and press releases will be published, as well as publications in conferences and presentation of project's results in conferences and events. In parallel, the final event will be organized in order to present overall the project's results.

2.3 Dissemination and Communication Goals

The first and one of the most important steps for setting up the communication and dissemination strategy for HEADSTART is to clearly define the goals to be pursued. In this way the communication and dissemination activities can be appropriately designed in order to target and meet these goals.

In short, the communication and dissemination activities will aim to:

- widely disseminate and diffuse the project concept and ideas at the early stage of the project and the project achievements and results at the mature stage of the project to the public;
- define and implement an integrated strategy to capture the project outputs and to communicate and disseminate them within industry and the research community;
- promote the results and findings to target audiences in the industrial, research and academic communities, and among regulatory and standardisation authorities;
- provide a regular flow of information about the project and its findings to the automotive industry and the research and academic community by publishing the project results to scientific journals and conference proceedings;
- facilitate effective communication and collaboration between research community and industry;
- foster dialogue with defined stakeholder groups and
- collaborate with international research networks and ongoing EU and national projects.

2.4 Audiences and approach

2.4.1 Target Audiences

The detailed definition of the communication & dissemination target groups is critical for directing resources to the most relevant and interested actors and maximizing the project impact on society. HEADSTART aspires to increase the involvement and results, while the findings and the acquired know-how are expected to be very critical for the sector of connected and automated mobility. The HEADSTART target groups are listed in Table 3 below.

TABLE 3, HEADSTART TARGET AUDIENCES

No.	Target Audience Groups	Objective	Expected Benefit
1	Industry & SMEs	To build relationships with SMEs and Industry in order to spread good practices and highlight the value of the project	A greater awareness of mobility considerations amongst SMEs and Industry and exposure to relevant data and services from the various H2020 projects.
2	Policy Makers & Public Authorities	To foster dialogue with defined policy makers and public bodies in order to promote connected and automated driving in particular and safe mobility in general.	Better policy making and decision making by public bodies, by capitalizing on useful data collected from experts, stakeholders and end-users.
3	Scientific & Research Community	To involve the Scientific Community in HEADSTART project in order to exchange knowledge, technologies and research about connected and automated mobility.	The acquisition and exchange of knowledge and expertise amongst the scientific and research community with regard to the CAD sector in general and in (safety) validation in particular.
4	International & EU associations and Working Groups	To foster dialogue with defined CAD stakeholder groups and promote the HEADSTART project within Europe and abroad.	International & EU associations will profit from a new project in CAD sector as well as its outcomes. Some of them are well represented within the consortium: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EuroNCAP members: IDIADA, TNO, BAST, AstaZero • Type approval: IDIADA and RDW are accredited Technical Services for Type Approval and support Member States in different WP 29 groups.

No.	Target Audience Groups	Objective	Expected Benefit
5	R&D Initiatives, Organizations and Technical Committees	To build relationships and involve other R&D initiatives, organizations and technical committees in order to gather input, exchange resources and data as well as to share best practices.	Added value to the network of R&D initiatives, organizations and committees by way of improved knowledge sharing and the dissemination of best practice. Within the consortium several partners are members of R&D organisations (e.g. EARPA, ERTICO and others) as well as Technical Committees (C-ITS platform, ERTRAC, etc.).
6	Standardization Bodies	To highlight the needs for missing standards or necessary regulation requirements and convince them that the adoption of HEADSTART testing and validation procedures will be of great benefit for the European automotive industry, the transport sector and for the uptake of automation in general.	Standardisation is a key driver for the future global CAD market update. It will enrich the reference market framework (actors, roles and interfaces), so that it is widely accepted and can evolve in time, and could be adopted as a reference in terms of policy efforts let at EC level. Several consortium members are already contributing in several Standardization bodies (ASAM, ETSI, ISO, etc..).
7	End Users	To raise awareness and build confidence to end users (drivers, owners, manufacturers) regarding the CAD mobility.	The end users to trust the CAD mobility as a safe and alternative form of mobility.
8	General Public	To raise awareness of HEADSTART project, its developments and benefits in CAD sector.	Awareness of the support and commitment of the EU to the deployment of CAD mobility.
9	Press & Media	To raise awareness and promote HEADSTART to the press & media in order to maximize impact in the scientific and industrial community and to engage more of the experts as well.	Scientific Press and Media will benefit from publications and news relevant to the connected and automated mobility sector.

2.4.2 Key messages per target audience

A set of key messages has been developed for each of the target audiences taking into account their needs and specifics at the start of the HEADSTART project, focusing on expected outputs. The key messages per target audience are listed in Table 4.

TABLE 4, HEADSTART KEY MESSAGES PER TARGET AUDIENCE

No.	Target Audience Groups	Key message
1	Industry & SMEs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> HEADSTART will develop its methodologies according to the key user's needs; HEADSTART does not aim to compete with existing or emerging solutions from industry and SMEs, but to complement, collaborate and link them towards a harmonized European solution. HEADSTART aims to involve experts of the CAD sector in order to co-design the methodologies, procedures and tools.
2	Policy Makers & Public Authorities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> HEADSTART through testing methodologies on defined use cases, will assist in defining clear strategies in Europe. HEADSTART will contribute to the deployment of safe and secure driving in Europe; HEADSTART will speed up the shift to automated driving;
3	Scientific & Research Community	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> HEADSTART aims to cooperate with the scientific and research community through the Expert Group. HEADSTART aims to communicate on research findings as well as to define further research topics.
4	International & EU associations and Working Groups	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> HEADSTART aims to bring together relevant initiatives, international and EU associations and Working Groups in order to collaborate towards a harmonized solution.
5	R&D Initiatives, Organizations and Technical Committees	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> HEADSTART aims to bring together R&D initiatives, organizations and technical committees in order to define technical topics (methodologies, tools, etc.) that need to be further worked on. HEADSTART will foster harmonization in order to avoid fragmentation. HEADSTART will identify gaps and overlaps.

No.	Target Audience Groups	Key message
6	Standardization Bodies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ HEADSTART will identify new standards to work on, based on its outcomes. ▪ HEADSTART will be aligned to new standards definition. ▪ HEADSTART will share its results and outcomes, highlight the gaps and propose new, harmonized solutions.
7	End Users	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ HEADSTART aims to increase safety. ▪ HEADSTART aims to improve competitiveness of the European industry.
8	General Public	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ HEADSTART aims to increase road safety.
9	Press & Media	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ HEADSTART aims to increase road safety. ▪ HEADSTART aims to speed up the shift to automated driving.

The key messages are expected to change during the project course to properly address new advances and be in line with the project developments.

3 Liaison and Networking activities

In order to ensure that HEADSTART reaches out to the right actors and produces outputs that are useful to stakeholders, a liaison team has been established lead by the WP5 leader, ERTICO. This team consists of 14 partners and is responsible for coordinating the exchange of results and know-how with other relevant R&I projects. In addition, WP5 is responsible for creating an Expert network, including the different types of CAD testing stakeholders and target groups, namely related clusters, R&D hubs, innovative SMEs and policy makers from around Europe and globally. The liaison team consists of the following three main entities:

- experts' platform;
- international cooperation platform;
- clustering platform.

The experts' platform for network will be open for experts external to the consortium to provide technical or strategic input on key activities of the project, such as user needs and requirements or the project approach to CAD testing methodology development.

The Network will be formed by different Working Groups according to the following topics: communications, cyber-security, positioning, scenario selection, consumer testing and type approval with the final aim to build consensus and maximize the HEADSTART impact.

The international cooperation platform is responsible to coordinate the communication with non-European initiatives. Furthermore, it will be the main platform to establish twinning activities through the steering and monitoring of the EC.

Finally, the clustering platform will be responsible for the synergies with ongoing projects, to share results, lessons learnt and best practices, identify gaps and avoid overlaps, but also with future initiatives so as to align the HEADSTART results to future research needs.

WP5 is responsible to coordinate the platforms as well as the organization of the events related to the liaison and networking activities. In this context, nine workshops with experts will be organized.

TABLE 5, NUMBER OF LIAISON ACTIVITIES PER YEAR AS IDENTIFIED IN THE GA

Type of dissemination activity	Year 1	Year 2	Year 3
Number of liaison activities to be performed	7	7	7

4 Key communication and dissemination tools & channels

The impact of the communication and dissemination activities will be amplified thanks to a set of specifically communication and dissemination tools & channels. These tools and channels will guarantee a coherent, wide and timely communication of the HEADSTART concept, objectives and solutions to reach multiple audiences and the general public. The following list (Table 6) summarises the tools and channels that will support all communication and dissemination activities.

TABLE 6, COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION TOOLS AND CHANNELS PER AUDIENCE

Tools	Audiences								
	Industry & SMEs	Policy Makers & Public Authorities	Scientific & Research Community	International & EU associations and Working Groups	R&D Initiatives, Organizations and Technical Committees	Standardization Bodies	End Users	General Public	Press & Media
Offline tools									
HEADSTART Brand Identity	X	X	X	X	X	X			X
Workshop	X	X	X	X	X	X			X
Demonstrations	X	X	X	X	X	X	X		
Conference	X	X	X	X	X	X			X
External Conferences	X	X	X	X	X	X	X		X

Tools	Audiences								
	Industry & SMEs	Policy Makers & Public Authorities	Scientific & Research Community	International & EU associations and Working Groups	R&D Initiatives, Organizations and Technical Committees	Standardization Bodies	End Users	General Public	Press & Media
Scientific Publications	X		X		X				X
Expert's Network	X	X	X	X	X	X			
Press Releases	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Press interview	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Press conferences	X	X	X	X	X	X			X
Print media (brochures, banners, etc.)	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	
Videos	X	X	X	X	X	X	X		X
Online tools									
Website	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Twitter Account	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
LinkedIn Account	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
LinkedIn page	X	X	X	X	X	X	X		X
Facebook page								X	
Blogs posts	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Online Newsletter	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X

Both online and offline tools and channels are employed so as new opportunities emerge along the project course.

4.1 Online communication and dissemination tools & channels

Recently, the online communication tends to be the most efficient method of promoting and disseminating events, projects, organizations etc. Therefore, online communication tools and channels (such as the website, social media, newsletter, etc.) are the main channels selected for HEADSTART communication and dissemination. Not only do they represent the best way to reach a wide audience at European and International levels at limited costs, but they also enable a more efficient and dynamic form of communication, while enabling to specify different messages to reach different target groups and give them the possibility to interact with the project and among themselves.

Below are listed some of the main online tools and channels to be used on HEADSTART.

4.1.1 Website

The HEADSTART website² is designed to be the backbone of the communications' activities, the main dissemination tool and gateway for everyone interested in the project as well as in connected and automated mobility in general.

Throughout the official website (Figure 3) the project and its ongoing activities are presented, as well as its results and outputs. It is designed in a way to guarantee ease of use and high level of accessibility and usability. Its structure ensures future scalability and quick expansion of the current structure. The full website is accessible at <https://www.headstart-project.eu/> since M3 and its detailed description is available in D6.1 Website.

For measuring the website effectiveness, the following KPIs related to this platform's number of visitors have been foreseen (Table 7).

TABLE 7, NUMBER OF VISITORS AND PAGE-VIEWS PER YEAR

Type of dissemination activity	Year 1	Year 2	Year 3
Website Visitors	800	1000	1200
Page-views for the website	6000	8000	12000

² HEADSTART D6.1 Website

FIGURE 3, THE HEADSTART WEBSITE'S HOMEPAGE

4.1.2 HEADSTART Social Media

Social networking sites are very important means of communication as they facilitate a direct conversation between the users, in order to disseminate the project's results and outputs, as well as share experience and participate in conversations about the project's issues. Recent surveys^{3 4} have proved that social media such as Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn, etc., are a popular online activity in terms of average time spent. Social media tend to be the most well-known means of communication, given their low cost, as well as the fact that within social media you can reach the general public.

To this end, HEADSTART designed and follows a coherent social media strategy for the best use of specific social media channels with basic purposes, as mentioned below:

- spread information about the project;
- maintain a professional and up-to-date profile;
- promote the experts' network;
- share and advertise interesting scientific and industrial developments and events;
- advertise partners' achievements;
- run effective campaigns to enhance the project's awareness, tackle key issues and promote the project's activities;

To this end, HEADSTART has already a quite active presence throughout Social Media. More specifically, a Twitter account, a LinkedIn account as well as a LinkedIn page have been established and also a Facebook page. ICCS, as Dissemination Manager, has the administration of all HEADSTART social media in order to share all partners' news, coordinate activities of partners and guarantee a coherent approach. The strategy defines the specific dissemination goals, the main messages, the hashtags, keywords, the tone, the frequency and the general tactic for posts.

The social media content will be written in English, as for all HEADSTART material, channels and tools. However, occasional posts in the partners' language will be allowed, where relevant. ICCS will oversee the daily management of these means and will ensure that at least three posts per social media site will be scheduled per week. The page's administrator will be also committed to like and be liked by relevant audience. To this end, all HEADSTART partners are responsible for increasing the potential of this channel. Besides, they are expected to send to the Task leader relevant content for publication and to contribute to its dissemination by following and sharing, as well as promoting the HEADSTART social media pages.

In addition, in the framework of running the social media accounts and in order to reinforce the project dissemination goals, targeted social media campaigns will take place. the campaigns will be designed in a

³ Social media: The new hybrid element of the promotion mix, W. Glynn Mangold, David J. Faulds, Business Horizons, Volume 52, Issue 4, July–August 2009, Pages 357-365, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bushor.2009.03.002>

⁴ Effectiveness of Social Media as a tool of communication and its potential for technology enabled connections: A micro-level study, Trisha Dowerah Baruah, International Journal of Scientific and Research Publications, Volume 2, Issue 5, May 2012 1 ISSN 2250-3153

targeted and measurable way. Within the project’s lifetime at least two social media campaigns will run, as identified in Table 8 following.

TABLE 8, NUMBER OF SOCIAL MEDIA CAMPAIGNS AS IS IDENTIFIED IN GA

Type of dissemination activity	Year 1	Year 2	Year 3
Social Media Campaigns		2	

More specifically, an action-gate campaign is planned to run by the end of the first year of the project’s lifetime. Within this campaign, the followers will be asked to interact with social media posts so as to increase interaction and enhance the partners’ and all interested parties’ involvement so as to create a sense of community. It will be an open campaign, where the participants will be asked to answer questions, take part in polls, provide reviews on specific topics, enter contests, etc.

A second campaign will start running in the middle of the project and for the rest of its lifetime. It will be a #hashtag campaign, inviting participants to upload their photos accompanied with a unique hashtag. This will result on the participants’ collaboration in order to create a “HEADSTART” album, easily accessible anytime and anywhere, with only requirement an internet connection.

Twitter account

The twitter account @HEADSTART_EU (Figure 4) is accessible at the following link: https://twitter.com/HEADSTART_EU . The channel primarily functions as a news source and a real-time conversation hub for trending topics. It is mostly used to raise awareness about the HEADSTART consortium, the project’s progress as well as to interact with key stakeholders and build relationships, disseminate the project’s news and current results. The twitter account follows EU institutions, agencies and officials, policy officers and staff linked to CAD sector, technology and H2020 themes, scientific and research organisations, industry representatives, public authorities, other H2020 CAD projects as well as other targeted audiences’ representatives. All the HEADSTART tweets will be automatically published on the website’s home page through a social stream.

In order to measure the Twitter effectiveness, the following target number of followers has been foreseen, as framed in the following table (Table 9).

TABLE 9, NUMBER OF FOLLOWERS IN TWITTER ACCOUNT

Type of dissemination activity	Year 1	Year 2	Year 3
Contacts on Twitter	100	200	300

FIGURE 4, HEADSTART TWITTER ACCOUNT

LinkedIn account & page

HEADSTART maintains both a LinkedIn group (Figure 5) and page (Figure 6) available at <https://www.linkedin.com/groups/8732558/> and <https://www.linkedin.com/company/13035375/admin/> respectively. LinkedIn hosting more than 500 million professional accounts thus tends to be the most popular social networking platform and the most powerful among professionals. This is the main reason we focus on this platform. The reason we maintain both a group and a page is that through the page we can further promote HEADSTART and also build a strong brand addressing a larger audience. Through the group we address our already established audience and we are able to share with them more specific information.

In order to measure the LinkedIn effectiveness, the following target number of followers has been foreseen in Grant Agreement as framed in the following table.

TABLE 10, HEADSTART LINKEDIN FOLLOWERS AS IDENTIFIED IN GA

Type of dissemination activity	Year 1	Year 2	Year 3
LinkedIn followers	40	80	150 followers

FIGURE 5, HEADSTART GROUP ON LINKEDIN

FIGURE 6, HEADSTART PAGE ON LINKEDIN

Facebook page

The Facebook page HeadstartEUproject (Figure 7) is available at the following link: https://www.facebook.com/HeadstartEUproject/?modal=admin_todo_tour For dissemination purposes, the HEADSTART Facebook channel is used mainly to connect with and engage general public.

FIGURE 7, HEADSTART PAGE ON FACEBOOK

4.1.3 Hashtags

Hashtags is a contemporary way to attract more eyes on social media posts. After a short empirical survey in Twitter, specific keywords appear to attract high impressions. The main keywords that arise and should be included on posts related to HEADSTART as highly responsive, are the following (figure 8): #vehicleautomation #security #connectedvehicles #connecteddriving #autonomousdriving #automatedvehicles #automateddriving #automation #InvestEUresearch #H2020 #EUTransportResearch #EUScienceInnov. It would be useful if these keywords should be used by all partners' social media, in order to get the HEADSTART project recognizable and also increase the number of followers. In addition, the specific hashtag #headstart4safety will be included in every post, and instructed so to all partners, so as to indicate the project.

FIGURE 8, HEADSTART RESPONSIVE HASHTAGS

4.1.4 Online newsletter

A subscribers list was started in parallel with the website’s launch. The list includes all people that have subscribed to it and expressed their interest in HEADSTART project and specifically in its newsletter. According to recent GDPR rules, these people have given their consent to receiving the HEADSTART news.

TABLE 11, NUMBER OF E-NEWSLETTER RECIPIENTS PER YEAR AS HAS BEEN IDENTIFIED IN GA

Type of dissemination activity	Year 1	Year 2	Year 3
Total number of e-newsletter recipients	50	100	150

To this end, the project will publish a periodic newsletter, every six months, starting after M12 onwards, to support the ongoing needs of the project after launching all the project’s activities. The newsletter’s objective is to summarize the project’s activities and outcomes and to proactively initiate conversations with multiple stakeholders about ongoing research topics. The e-newsletters will include information about the project’s process and will address the scientific community as well as SMEs and Industry.

4.2 Offline communication and dissemination tools & channels

In addition to the online communication tools and channels, offline communication tools and channels will be provided in order to disseminate the project in a more tangible and extensive way. More specifically, the HEADSTART brand identity will be defined as well as the “architecture” of the printed material and communication activities.

4.2.1 Brand Identity

The HEADSTART project will build a strong project identity through effective branding and the delivery of clear messages to a variety of target audiences including a project logo and the use of consistent and professional promotional materials. To this end and in order to maintain the integrity of the project, HEADSTART has configured its own Brand Book, including information such as the project’s brand name, brand description, logos variety, graphic elements, typography elements, etc. which provide extensive information on how the brand will be communicated to the target audiences.

4.2.2 HEADSTART Logo

The core element of the HEADSTART Brand Identity is the HEADSTART logo (Figure 9). The logo icon represents the final aim of the project, the validation, through specific functionalities/activities. The font to be used follows the modern, minimal design, harmonically fitting with the icon. The imaginary line that comes across the letters, symbolizes the harmony and continuity as the final aim. The light black line highlights the word ‘HEAD’ as the beginning and the peak of actions, while the differentiation of the letters AD in bold emphasizes on the objective (Automated Road). The colour palette (gradient colour) as well represents the simultaneity/harmony and the transition from the initial action to the final validation.

FIGURE 9, THE HEADSTART LOGO

All the logo elements, as well as the logo variations, the colour palette, the brand typography, the logo usage on social media and on backgrounds as well as other additional information are described on details within the already developed BrandBook (Annex 1).

4.2.3 Project Templates

A set of HEADSTART MS office templates has been created based on the project brand in order to be used in all internal and external events so as to safeguard an homogeneity. More specifically, a ppt template has been prepared in order to be used by all partners when presenting the project internally, as well as to third parties, unless an event specifies another format (e.g. a conference template that is obligatory for that event) (Annex 1). In addition, a word template has been prepared for submitting the HEADSTART Deliverables (Annex 1) as well as a Minutes template for keeping minutes within the consortium virtual or physical meetings (Annex 1).

4.2.4 Printed Material

HEADSTART dissemination efforts will be also supported by a set of printed material. An initial version of the dissemination material will be prepared for the end of the 1st year, starting from the middle of the project. However, a standard presentation is already available for all partners to use. Its purpose is to support partners

on their individual presentations when participating in external events and will be updated regularly, depending on the project's progress and the achieved results. The presentation is in a short and a long version too, including information such as: the project's concept, objectives and facts, the main activities and expected impact as well as the consortium and contact information.

Besides the HEADSTART general presentation, general information about the project will be provided by the project's brochure and the roll-up banner.

One of the most prominent ways for disseminating the project's ideas, results and concepts is the project brochure. The brochure of the project is a non-electronic means of providing summary information on the project activities and expected achievements. The brochure will be distributed to conferences, workshops, special events, etc. It will provide a short overview of the main features, objectives and expected impact of the project. It will also provide links and contacts for further information. Its aim is to reach both the scientific and industrial audience and the general public. Thus, the information provided is kept as simple as possible, explaining in short, the concept, ideas and scheduled activities including a set of images and icons as well.

In addition to the brochure, a HEADSTART roll-up banner will be developed. The banner will be used at project or external events as a visual attraction. It will contain only short information on the project while it will follow the same graphic concept as the brochure, based on the HEADSTART brand identity.

4.2.5 Press Activities

A press and media strategy, including press activities at significant HEADSTART milestones, will be followed in order to raise awareness and generate positive media coverage for the project at a local, national and European level. Within its lifetime, HEADSTART will make every effort to forward announcements and press releases to the mass media, such as TV scientific programmes, but also to the press. Given the mass media significant power, the project will try to exploit any opportunity to reach the wider public. All messages to the media will be short and comprehensible, in layman's language so as to be easily understood by the unexperienced audience.

Any partner proposing public output (e.g. news, articles, press releases, presentations or papers at events, etc.) must follow the HEADSTART dissemination procedures (Section 8 & Annex 2), which aim to ensure high quality and consistent output, to avoid overlaps, conflicting messages or possible disclosure of confidential information and to help monitor project dissemination activities. This involves an approval process prior to dissemination taking place involving at least the Project Coordinator and the DCM, and where appropriate, the Steering Committee.

The press activities may include: press releases, news articles, interviews, media campaigns and events, etc.

Press Releases

During its duration, HEADSTART will make every effort to prepare and forward press releases and announcements about interesting news to the mass media and the press.

Press releases will be published by the consortium at key moments during the lifetime of the project. The Dissemination Manager in consultation with the Coordinator, will draft the press releases in English and forward them to all partners. In the case that other partners are involved in the press release, the Dissemination Manager will forward them the press release beforehand so as to confirm their agreement or edit accordingly.

It is up to any partner to translate the press release in their local language so as to be distributed to the national media contacts and reach the local audiences.

All partners are requested to share the press releases in all their available channels towards their audiences so as to boost the project's/achievement's awareness.

A first press release was prepared by ICCS and distributed to all partners regarding the launch of the project and the kick-off meeting held in Brussels, on 23 & 24 January 2019 (Annex 1).

News Articles

During the 3 years of the project, the consortium will produce and publish articles to get media interest and encourage magazine to publish articles on the project's concept, progress and results. Whenever an article is not written by the Dissemination Manager and/or the Project Coordinator, a copy of the article and press release should be sent to ICCS. Relevant press clippings will be included on the HEADSTART website.

TABLE 12, NEWS ARTICLES

Event	Date	Type of publication/presentation	Partner
Notice in "Elektroniktidningen"	07/05/2019	Notice in magazine for electronics	SAFER
Notice in "Elektroniktidningen"	07/05/2019	Notice in magazine for electronics	SAFER

Articles and Interviews

HEADSTART partners, led by the project's Dissemination Manager, will write articles and interviews for inclusion on the website. In addition, each partner is able to write and publish an article in an external media. In this case, the partner should inform the Dissemination Manager and the Project Coordinator, at least 2 weeks before publication, accordingly to the Dissemination Procedures (Section 8).

Media campaigns and events

Around key project events special media campaigns may be launched. These may include press invitations/announcements and press events.

Press announcements/invitations aim to invite the media to participate in the events or to inform them about the events taking place, as well as to provide them with an overview of the project's objectives. The press invitation/announcements will be drafted by the Dissemination Manager with the contribution of the local partner(s)'s press office. It will be sent to the media at least 5 days before the event. The content should be short, clear, present the HEADSTART project, the event and the benefits of the project. The press announcement will be in English, but local press offices may translate it into other languages.

If there is sufficient press interest, a press conference will be organised involving a range of high-level key project stakeholders. It will last around 30 minutes (depending on the number of speakers) and it will be followed by a Q&A session, as well as a networking event. One-to-one interviews with the speakers can also be organised.

The press conference will be either in English and/or in the local language. At the press conference, dissemination and promotional material will be available (brochure, press release of the event, etc.). If a press conference is not organised or not considered as the best means to promote HEADSTART then another event/activity relevant to the press (workshop, networking breakfast, one-to-one interviews, etc.) will be organised.

In the context of the final event, a press conference will be held, so as to promote the project's results and solutions in media and non-technical audiences.

4.2.6 Scientific publications

HEADSTART results will be published in peer-reviewed scientific journals, in relevant industrial and trade magazines, as well as technical papers in conferences. Open access of HEADSTART publications will be prioritised, for example through open access publications such as Transportation Research Procedia (Elsevier), the International Journal of ITS Research (Springer) or the ESR Journal, excluding those who require payment of substantial fees to ensure open access. Some project partners may have existing open access publishing agreements with some journals and this will be explored internally.

The publications will be uploaded in the HEADSTART website, in the corresponding section. In the case that a full article cannot be uploaded to the website, the abstract will be provided with a link to the appropriate journal if available.

The consortium aims to make use, whenever possible and always after consultation with the PO, of the European Commission means, such as the Horizon Magazine, the research*eu results magazine, Futuris Magazine, etc., in order to increase awareness about the project’s outputs around major milestones.

TABLE 13, JOURNAL ARTICLES PER YEAR

Type of dissemination activity	Year 1	Year 2	Year 3
Scientific publications	≥1	≥2	≥3

To assist the partners in planning their dissemination activities, a list of relevant conferences is already created and available in the project’s repository (Annex 3). The list will be regularly updated to include further dissemination opportunities, while relevant information will be sent by the WP6 leader to the consortium on a regular basis via direct mailing. In addition to this list, a list with scientific journals will be created for the same purposes.

5 Key communication activities

Several activities will be organised within the lifetime of the project in order to support community building, foster cooperation between relevant actors and widely promote European activities in the area of connected and automated mobility. More specifically, the workshops as well as the demonstrations are of the most important activities that will take place. The objective of such activities is to engage stakeholders and liaise with national and international initiatives and standardization working groups.

5.1 Expert’s Workshops

A set of 9 workshops with the Expert Network working groups will be organised through the course of the project, to reach consensus on key priorities in CAD validation. The workshops purposes are to collect stakeholder needs and requirements, analyse the gaps and weaknesses to define priorities in future research needs for CAD testing, but also to validate the project approach in general.

HEADSTART workshops are an important tool for the project as one of its objectives is the consensus building between CAD stakeholders towards the (safety) validation of road automation. The workshops will support the analysis, harmonization, development and demonstration objectives of the project and will act both as a communication and dissemination tool. The expert workshops will be organized in the context of WP5 activities

and its location and agenda shall be agreed between the WP5 leader and the chairs and co-chairs of the different subgroups that are encompassed in the Expert Group. These workshops will be topic based, that is, each of them will be organized a certain topic or topics that are considered of relevance e.g. for the harmonization or development needs of the project, normally associated to the Expert group sub-groups. In general terms, the workshops should:

1. Present the HEADSTART project in general and in particular for the topic(s) under discussion
2. Present the status of the project activities and its (intermediate) results
3. Foster information sharing among the experts
4. Foster consensus building in a certain topic
5. Receive indications from the experts when the project requires to steer its activities

Moreover, the workshops will facilitate the interaction between experts, projects and ongoing initiatives in the field of CAD testing. They will also be another tool to promote the project results and thus facilitate their adoption.

5.2 Demonstrations

Demonstrations are a key dissemination tool of the project. Within these demonstrations two main objectives are pursued:

1. Execute in a proving ground environment the procedures developed within the project for the selected use cases.
2. Show to the audience the benefits of using the project results for validation and testing of CAD

Three demonstrations are foreseen in the project. Their agenda will highly depend on the required activities to be performed and the selected use cases that will be validated. In general terms, the demonstrations should:

- Execute the different test procedures developed in the project and assess its results
- Promote the project objectives among its target audience. The target audience (e.g. experts, policy makers, general audience) will be defined in advance and consequently, the demonstrations organisation and agenda will be adapted to them

Physical demonstrations of any kind are a powerful communication and dissemination tool that may attract a high number of attendees. For this reason, demonstrations may be linked to workshops as well as other communication and dissemination tools. Different proving grounds in Europe will be chosen due to technical decisions but also to reach broader dissemination of the project.

The organization and execution of the demonstrations are responsibility of the partners involved in WP4 with the support of the rest of WPs.

6 Dissemination Roadmap

The selection of the appropriate dissemination channel and the respective message to be disseminated heavily depends on the stage in which the project is at each specific moment.

During the early phases of the project, the concept and the vision of the research work are mainly conveyed since no results are available yet. On the other hand, towards the end of the project, more technical presentations and publications can be realized as new developments will be achieved. The dissemination roadmap provides a draft outline of the way that the dissemination channels and materials are going to be used for reaching each of the specified target group throughout the duration of the project.

The following sections provide an overview of the dissemination activities' plan per year.

6.1 1st year Dissemination Activities

During the first year of HEADSTART, the dissemination activities aim to generally inform the public, relevant research, academic and industrial communities on the project's objectives and expected outcomes and results. These activities will set the basis for the whole dissemination policy to be followed, since most of the dissemination material will be produced at this stage and also be used for the whole duration of the project.

Within the first year of the project, the informative brochure and the banner will be designed and are going to be disseminated in various events. In addition, the website, which is already live, is going to be frequently updated according to the project's needs and developments as well as the social media accounts will be constantly enriched with interesting news and posts. Moreover, we plan to boost the project's awareness with press activities focused on major milestones – we have already issued a press release for the kickoff meeting and the launch of the project activities and we plan to issue a second one presenting the 1st HEADSTART workshop's results - as well as with news clips whenever needed.

In addition, publications and presentations will be issued which, given the early stage of the project, will mainly include information about the project's concept and research methodology to be followed.

Finally, given that we plan to establish the Expert's Network, we will make a special effort to engage with experts. However, at this stage, it would be meaningless to limit the target audience to one specific group. For this scope, we plan to address a broad range of stakeholders so that they get informed about the project's existence and objectives, as well as the benefits of participating in the Network.

6.2 2nd year Dissemination Activities

Already from the second year of the project some initial results will be available. Thus, the aim of dissemination within this period will be to publish the first developments and describe the future work to be performed.

The research community, technical committees, policy-making authorities and decision-making stakeholders, end users, etc., will form the main target groups of the publications and project presentations to be performed during this that year. More technical papers will be submitted to scientific conferences as well as to workshops and events.

In addition, a series of workshops will be organized every year starting from the first year, in order to validate different things at different stages of the project. While the first-year workshops aim to identify the real needs and establish the methodologies and procedures to be followed within the project; the second-year workshops will aim to efficiently disseminate its preliminary findings and collect feedback.

Last but not least, additional dissemination material will be developed pending on the project's specific needs in the second year while the website and social media will be continuously be updated with newer project achievements. e-newsletters will also be issued to inform all interested parties about the latest news and developments.

6.3 3rd year Dissemination Activities

During the final year of HEADSTART, there will be a major effort of disseminating the project results to all target groups using every available dissemination channel.

Within the third and last year of the project, technical papers presenting the final results of HEADSTART will be published to various International and European scientific conferences, while demonstrations of the available tools will be included at relevant events and exhibitions. In addition, live demos of the developments can be presented at various conferences and events.

A strong effort will be given to press releases and mass media involvement so as to transmit the HEADSTART messages and developments to wider audiences. Finally, and as always, the website and social media will continuously be updated with latest developments and information. Last but not least, the final deliverables will be available to download by all interested parties on the website.

6.4 After the project's end Dissemination Activities

Even after the project termination there is still a high possibility to enhance the project impact to the community. All final results will be available for exploitation which will be facilitated by appropriate dissemination activities, such as scientific publications for example.

The HEADSTART website will be sustained for at least 5 years after the end of the project in order to provide all interested stakeholders with information on project achievements and results and details on contact persons.

7 Events

7.1 HEADSTART Project Events

Within the lifetime of the project a number of HEADSTART events are proposed so as to communicate further the HEADSTART messages and disseminate its findings and results.

7.1.1 Stakeholders' Workshop

More specifically, WP6 plans to one stakeholders' workshop. The workshop is planned for the period after the middle of the project, i.e. after M18, in order to attract a wide number of related experts coming mainly from the HEADSTART Experts Network. The workshop will be organised in collaboration with WP5 so as to engage stakeholders and liaise with national and international initiatives and standardization working groups. Further than disseminating the preliminary findings of the project, the workshop aims to collect feedback from key-stakeholders, involving all Working Groups for WP5, as an opportunity to further promote its activities and actions, such as the Expert Network.

7.1.2 Final Event

A final event is planned for the end of the project, on M36. The scope of the final event is to present the project's results. It is expected to be one of the major dissemination activities within the lifetime of the project, aiming to attract more than 100 participants. Technical speeches and live demonstrations will take place in order to promote exclusively the HEADSTART outcomes and showcase the developed technologies. In parallel, an exhibition will take place. In the context of the final event, a press conference will be held, so as to promote the project's results and solutions in media and non-technical audiences.

All materials of the events organised in the framework of HEADSTART project, such as presentations, reports, specific dissemination material, etc., will be open and available on the HEADSTART website.

7.2 External Events

HEADSTART presentations and demonstrations will be organized at specialized meetings and congresses, to broadly disseminate the project's concept, its findings and outcomes among the experts' communities. The consortium has already identified a set of related conferences that take place during the running of HEADSTART.

To assist the partners in planning their dissemination activities, a list of relevant conferences is already created and available in the project's repository (Annex 3). The list will be regularly updated to include further dissemination opportunities, while relevant information will be sent by the WP6 leader to the consortium on a regular basis via direct mailing.

Moreover, a number of HEADSTART special sessions will be organised in the context of important and well-known conferences, such as the ITS European and World Congresses, the TRA & TRB conferences, etc. In order

to measure the HEADSTART participation, the following target number of special sessions has been foreseen (Table 14) as framed in the following table.

TABLE 14, NUMBER OF SPECIAL SESSIONS PER YEAR

Type of dissemination activity	Year 1	Year 2	Year 3
Organization of workshops/ special sessions	1	1	2

All materials of the special sessions such as presentations, reports, etc., will be available on the HEADSTART website.

HEADSTART has already been disseminated through presentations in conferences and events, as presented in the table below (Table 15).

TABLE 15, HEADSTART PARTICIPATION IN EVENTS & CONFERENCES

Event	Date	Presentation Content	Presentation
ARCADE workshop (Brussels)	05/02/2019	General information of the project	Nicolas Wagener (IKA)
JRC workshop on certification (Brussels)	07/03/2019	General information of the project	Ilona Cieslik (IDIADA)
ARCADE workshop (Brussels)	04/04/2019	General information of the project	Álvaro Arrúe (IDIADA)
EU/US/Japan ART group (Brussels)	05/04/2019	General information of the project	Álvaro Arrúe (IDIADA)
Jornada del vehículo industrial de STA (Barcelona)	14/05/2019	General information of the project	Álvaro Arrúe (IDIADA)
Autonomous Vehicle Symposium (Stuttgart)	22/05/2019	General information of the project	Álvaro Arrúe (IDIADA)

Event	Date	Presentation Content	Presentation
ITS European Congress	04/06/2019	General information of the project	Álvaro Arrúe (IDIADA), Jacco van de Sluis (TNO)

8 Dissemination Procedures – Partner’s Roles

8.1 Dissemination Procedures

The participation of any Partner in an event as well as the performance of every dissemination activity related to the HEADSTART project has to be approved beforehand by the Project Coordinator and the Dissemination Manager. The Dissemination Manager supports the Project Coordinator and the Consortium in planning and monitoring the dissemination activities.

The objectives for this monitoring and control are to:

- produce high quality HEADSTART publications and presentations;
- avoid overlaps and possible disclosure of restricted or confidential information;
- monitor and record the dissemination activities of the project in a sufficient way.

In general, the following are considered as dissemination activities:

- Submission of papers in relevant Journals;
- Submission of presentations in Conferences;
- Articles published in the popular press
- Participation in exhibitions via stands and demonstrators;
- Organisation of project workshops;
- Organisation of special sessions in conferences;
- Production of newsletters, leaflets, posters, etc.;
- Sending out of press releases;
- Media briefings;
- Public project presentations;
- Participation in non-project workshops, forums and/or events;
- Announcements on websites/applications;
- Flyers;
- Videos;
- Interviews;
- TV clips;
- Etc.

Each partner wishing to perform a dissemination activity relevant to HEADSTART has to follow a simple procedure, which is described below. The stepwise procedure to be followed is:

1. Fill in the spaces of the table; (Annex 2)
2. Store the material (abstract, draft paper, poster etc.) to the BOX online repository⁵;

⁵ This is the online collaboration tool of the HEADSTART consortium. The access is restricted as it includes confidential information and this deliverable (D6.2) is public.

3. Submit your dissemination request providing for minimum two weeks before submission deadline by email to the WP6 Leader (Mrs. Nikoletta Karitsioti)
4. WP6 Leader has 2 days to react and send the request to Coordinator/SC for approval, modification or rejection;
5. Coordinator/SC decision send to the WP6 Leader within five working days; If no answer is received due to the set deadline it is taken as an approval;
6. WP6 Leader informs the involved partner(s) about the decision.

In case of:

A) Approval: When approval is given through the WP6 Leader the partner(s) are free to proceed with the realisation of the proposed dissemination activity;

B) Conflict/objection: Any SC member can reject the proposed dissemination activity if they have objections, related to overlaps or possible disclosure of restricted or confidential information concern the work performed in the different WPs. In case of conflict, the issue is being discussed among the coordinator, the WP6 Leader and the involved partners;

**If a conflict is created or further material is needed then WP6 Leader informs the partner and requires modifications or additions. Then the material is proposed again to WP6 Leader and if significant changes that might provoke conflicts among partners' interests must be made, the previous procedure is followed.

Within ten working days after the realisation of the approved dissemination activity, the partner should provide the WP6 Leader (nikoletta.karitsioti@iccs.gr;) with the filled in dissemination report and the presented dissemination material (final paper, presentation, poster etc.). It will be highly appreciated if the respective partner provides in addition pictures from the event. The dissemination report form is stored in the BOX online repository. All material will be archived by ICCS to the BOX online repository ([link](#)). All material will be archived by ICCS to the BOX online repository.

NOTE:

- If partners wish to present or release material already approved as public presentation and material then no formal approval is required. The WP6 Leader (nikoletta.karitsioti@iccs.gr;) has to be informed. If there are no objections, then the WP6 Leader notifies the authors to proceed with the dissemination activity.
- In case a partner wishes to organise a workshop or special event related to HEADSTART, then the approval of WP6 Leader and the information of the Coordinator and the SC is also needed 2 months before the realisation of this dissemination activity.

Non-European Travel

** For non-European travels the PO should be informed and an approval from his side is required. Please fill-in the Non-European Travel Report Template at least two months before the travel and send the form to the project Coordinator (Mr. Alvaro Arrue) so as to inform the EC. For possible enquiry by the auditors in the future it is recommended to keep the form and EC's response with the respective travel documents.

Disclaimer & acknowledgement of the EC funding

"This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 824309. Content reflects only the authors' view and European Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains."

For other communication activities, the EC emblem should be included with the phrase:

“This work is a part of the HEADSTART project. This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 824309”

For infrastructure, equipment & major results, the EC emblem should be included as well as the phrase:

“This [infrastructure][equipment][insert type of result] is part of HEADSTART project that has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 824309”

For correct use of the EC emblem the partners should consult the following links:

- European flag:

http://europa.eu/about-eu/basic-information/symbols/flag/index_en.htm

- Commission's guidelines on visual identity:

http://ec.europa.eu/research/fp7/index_en.cfm?pg=logos

8.2 Dissemination records

In order to keep a record of all the dissemination efforts of the HEADSTART consortium, it is beneficial to keep an online record where all partners will be able to add their effort. More specifically an online excel will be uploaded in the online repository (BOX) providing information about the events the partners participated, their presentations, etc.

The WP6 Task Leader is responsible for reminding all partners via bimonthly emails to fill in the table, while all partners are obliged to fill in the excel with all the required information.

8.3 Partner’s Roles

All partners involved in the HEADSTART consortium are charged with responsibilities, even specific tasks. This section aims to describe extensively all partners’ roles in order to safeguard the effective collaboration and maximize the project’s impact.

8.3.1 WP6 Responsibilities

WP6 “Communication and Dissemination” consists of 3 tasks and more sub-tasks. Each of these tasks has a specific Task Leader who will be supported by one or more other consortium partners with resources in this particular task.

ICCS carries overall responsibility for WP6 activities. It also leads Task 6.1 Dissemination and Communication Strategy and Task 6.2: Communication Channels and Outreach. Within Task 6.1 will be designed the Communication and Dissemination Strategy of the project as well as will be deployed its brand identity. Within Task 6.2, will be determined the appropriate channels and tools, so as to address effectively all the targeted audiences.

In the following table (Table 16) are listed all partners that participate in WP6, having the corresponding responsibilities.

TABLE 16, PARTICIPATION PER PARTNER

Partners	Effort
IDIADA	11.00

Partners	Effort
CRF	3.00
ICCS	20.00
SAFER	2.00
TNO	1.00
VALEO	1.00
VEDECOM	2.00
VICOMTECH	4.00
VIF	4.00
Total	48.00

8.3.2 Communication and Dissemination Manager

The HEADSTART Communication and Dissemination Manager (ICCS) will work closely with the Project Coordinator for the best communication of the project’s vision, objectives and outcomes to the media and external stakeholders. The Communication & Dissemination Manager will be the main contact point for the media and external stakeholders; responsible for communicating at European level and will work closely together with pilot site leaders and relevant consortium partners in the organization of events, coordination of articles and translations. ICCS will regularly communicate with leaders of active tasks/WPs in order to gather information that can be used for news items and validate such news items with the task/WP leaders and the Coordinator. In addition, ICCS will report on the communication and dissemination achievements and progress when and where it is necessary and also will define and monitor the partners’ work plan for communication and dissemination.

8.3.3 HEADSTART Dissemination Group

For the better organization and functionality of WP6, a HEADSTART Dissemination Group has been established. The group consists of the WP6 partners as well as partners involved in other WPs linked to WP6, such as WP1 and WP5. The WP6 Dissemination Group will work closely to discuss specific communication and dissemination issues such as the expert’s network and how it can be promoted, the events’ organization, the special promotion material production, etc.

To this early stage of the project, the WP6 Dissemination Group together with the Project Coordinator, is organizing monthly teleconferences so as to discuss the communication and dissemination issues.

8.3.4 HEADSTART project event organizing committees

For each of the HEADSTART events (Section 7), a small organizing committee will be established, consisted of project partners. Each organizing committee, under the Communication and Dissemination Manager leadership, will work towards the event’s organization, determining the events needs such as the venue, the agenda, the title and the theme of event, etc.

8.3.5 All partners

All partners will contribute with inputs to news and articles for the website, for the event's calendar and also for the printed material when required. In the absence of regular news from active tasks or partners, the Communication and Dissemination Manager will prompt the Task leaders for potentially newsworthy updates. They will report their project-related communication activities to ICCS by including information regarding the events which they attended and are planning to attend in their management report. Consortium partners will report on their dissemination activities, according to the dissemination procedures (Section 8).

Partners intending to participate in one of the events listed in the Calendar of Events, or another event relevant to the HEADSTART topic, shall notify the Task Leader giving all the details for the event. In the case that a specific communication related to HEADSTART project is proposed (such as a technical paper, a special session, etc.) this shall be notified to the Communication and Dissemination Manager and be subject to the project's dissemination procedures.

Even if a partner is attending a relevant event without any planned HEADSTART communication and not charging any costs to the project, notification to the Communication and Dissemination Manager is requested in case of possible networking opportunities or the possibility to distribute HEADSTART material (brochures, etc.).

Furthermore, all partners are expected to promote the project to their network by all available channels and means. Finally, in order to reach the social media and website targets set on GA, all partners should promote the HEADSTART social accounts, as well as the news list and the website.

8.3.6 Timing of official WP6 Deliverables

In the following table (Table 17) are presented all the WP6 Deliverables, the responsible partner as well as the due date.

TABLE 17, WP6 DELIVERABLES

Deliverable Title	Dissemination level	Partner	Due Date
D6.1 Website	PU	ICCS	M3
D6.2 Dissemination and Communication strategy	PU	ICCS	M6
D6.3 Dissemination and Communication strategy: review	PU	ICCS	M19
D6.4 Dissemination and Communication strategy: beyond HEADSTART	PU	ICCS	M36
D6.5 Dissemination material: First year	PU	ICCS	M12
D6.6 Dissemination material: Second year	PU	ICCS	M24
D6.7 Dissemination material: Third year	PU	ICCS	M36

Deliverable Title	Dissemination level	Partner	Due Date
D6.8 Report on efforts towards standardisation	PU	IDIADA	M36

More specifically, the D6.1 Website includes the design and implementation of the official HEADSTART website. This Deliverable was submitted on time on European Commission for approval, while the website is up and running.

The D6.2 ‘Dissemination and Communication strategy’ aims to define the overall HEADSTART Dissemination and Communication Strategy as well as to plan the future activities. The plan is to be updated frequently. After these updated new Deliverables will occur.

Specifically, on M19, the D6.3 ‘Dissemination and Communication strategy: review’ which will be an update of the dissemination and communication strategy taking advantage of newer opportunities and initial assessment of the effectiveness of the HEADSTART channels to reach specific target audiences.

In addition, on M36 the D6.4 ‘Dissemination and Communication strategy: beyond HEADSTART’ will be submitted, including a detailed report of all the performed communication and dissemination activities presenting their overall impact.

The Deliverable D6.5 ‘Dissemination material: First year’, linked to the D6.2 ‘Dissemination and Communication Strategy’ will present the project’s brand identity exclusively, while in parallel will include the dissemination material provided for the dissemination needs of the project.

The D6.6 ‘Dissemination material: Second year’ is expected to be an updated version of the dissemination material including relevant updates according to the project’s progress.

The D6.7 ‘Dissemination material: Third year’ will present the final version of the dissemination material.

Last but not least, the D6.8 ‘Report on efforts towards standardization’ will report on the efforts to approach standardisation bodies to the HEADSTART results and promote the project outcomes and findings.

9 Conclusions

Communication and dissemination activities are of a major importance for HEADSTART project and therefore a significant number of activities is planned within its lifetime. In order to coordinate these activities, there is a need for a concise dissemination strategy.

The present deliverable underlines the Communication and Dissemination Strategy which will be adapted as the project evolved. This Strategy also defines the project's communication and dissemination goals as well as the specified audiences and use the most appropriate means to achieve them, communicate the project and make all the results and deliverables of the project available to the stakeholders and to the appropriate audiences. All the aforementioned elements are combined in a concise roadmap that is supervised by the Dissemination Manager according to specific procedures.

For the implementation of the Communication and Dissemination Strategy, the contribution of all HEADSTART partners is required. More specifically, all partners will be tasked to support the development and dissemination of the communication material, by providing feedbacks, local contacts, translations and all types of content requested by the Task leader in order to ensure the effectiveness of the strategy. In addition, partners will be responsible to attend events that are related with their specifications, keeping in mind the guidelines provided in this document and disseminate the material in their communications channels, for instance, websites, social media, newsletters, events, etc.

Concluding, and taking into consideration all above-mentioned, the Communication and Dissemination Strategy will be a live document to be updated in the course of the project. The necessary adaptations will be reflected at periodic review meetings with the EU. The D6.2 'Dissemination and Communication Strategy' will be updated in D6.3 'Dissemination and Communication strategy: review', which will be submitted in M19.

10 References

1. EU Grants: H2020 Guidance – Social media guide for EU funded R&I projects: v1.0 – 06.04.2018 Available at: http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/other/grants_manual/amga/soc-med-guide_en.pdf (last access 21/06/2019)
2. HEADSTART D6.1 Website
3. W. Glynn Mangold, David J. Fauldsb (2009), Social media: The new hybrid element of the promotion mix, Business Horizons, Volume 52, Issue 4, July–August 2009, Pages 357-365, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bushor.2009.03.002>
4. Trisha Dowerah Baruah (2012), Effectiveness of Social Media as a tool of communication and its potential for technology enabled connections: A micro-level study, International Journal of Scientific and Research Publications, Volume 2, Issue 5, May 2012 1 ISSN 2250-3153

Annex 1: Communication and dissemination material

HEADSTART Brand identity

HEADSTART Logo

HEADSTART Logo for Social Media

Brand Identity Guidelines
Master Logo

Concept / The idea behind

HEADSTART (Harmonised European Solutions for Testing Automated Road Transport)

First of all, the logo icon represents the final aim of the project, the validation, through specific functionalities/activities. The font to be used in HEADSTART follows the modern, minimal design, harmonically fitting with the icon. The imaginary line that comes across the letters, symbolizes the harmony and continuity as the final aim. The light black line highlights the word 'HEAD' as the beginning and the peak of actions, while the differentiation of the letters AD in bold emphasizes on the objective (Automated Road). The colour palette (gradient colour) as well represents the simultaneity/harmony and the transition from the initial action to the final validation.

3

Brand Identity Guidelines
Brand Typography

Primary Typeface
Din pro Regular

The primary typeface is DIN pro with a secondary Nunito Sans ExtraLight to complement the primary. These two typefaces have been carefully selected to give prominence to the brand image, and must be always used to retain consistency - especially within the logo. Replacing fonts with alternatives should not be done under any circumstances. It is strongly recommended for consistency reasons to use these two typefaces for any type of HEADSTART promotional material and in web media and applications.

Secondary Typeface
Nunito Sans ExtraLight

Din pro fonts family

- Regular ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
- Italic ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz*

1. Bold ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz

1. Bold Italic ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz

<http://freakfonts.com/fonts/dinproregular2320.html?fbclid=IwAR0oqtvoybuwv70ob-ddadjpunupi6sd4byycgb-9i5mvpkwxkav0vh8q>

Nunito Sans ExtraLight

- Regular ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
- Italic ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz*

<https://fonts.google.com/specimen/Nunito+Sans>

4

1) For MS templates and publications

HEADING 1
DinPro Bold- 18pt
HEADING 2
DinPro Bold - 16pt
 (RGB= R25 G85 B166)
HEADING 3
DinPro Bold - 14pt
 (RGB= R25 G85 B166)
HEADING 4
DinPro Bold - 12pt
 (RGB= R25 G85 B166)
 Body Text
 DinPro Regular- 11pt

2) For Website and other web-applications

HEADING 1
DinPro Bold - 18pt
HEADING 2
DinPro Bold - 16pt
 (RGB= R25 G85 B166)
HEADING 3
DinPro Bold - 14pt
 (RGB= R25 G85 B166)
HEADING 4
DinPro Bold - 12pt
 (RGB= R25 G85 B166)
 Body Text
 DinPro Regular- 11pt

3) For leaflets and other material

HEADING 1
DinPro Bold - 18pt
HEADING 2
DinPro Bold - 16pt
 (CMYK= 95C, 75M)
HEADING 3
DinPro Bold - 14pt
 (CMYK= 95C, 75M)
HEADING 4
DinPro Bold - 12pt
 (CMYK= 95C, 75M)
 Body Text
 DinPro Regular- 10pt

5

Positive

Primarily the logo should be used on a white background in its positive format for maximum impact and clarity. This primary format is used in every occasion except from the cases it is not feasible. In these cases, the following versions are available for usage:

Negative

This format of the HEADSTART logo is only used when placing the logo on an image, a colored background or a pattern.

6

Brand Identity Guidelines | Logo Variations

BW/Grayscale Formats

These logo variations are meant to be printed in a grayscale or black and white format (i.e. internal memos).

BW / Grayscale Positive Format

Used on a light background

BW / Grayscale Negative Format

Used on a dark background

7

Brand Identity Guidelines | Colour Palette

CMYK colours are used in printing material
RGB colours are used on web applications

BLUE COLOUR PALETTE

 CMYK= 30C RGB= R171 G225 B250 #abe1fa			
---	---	--	---

PURPLE COLOUR

 CMYK= 27C, 80M
 RGB= R185 G86 B160
 #b956a0

Secondary

 CMYK= 7C, 23M RGB= R230 G201 B225 #e6c9e1		
--	--	--

Additional colour palette can be used for layouts and artworks such as website/posters/leaflets e.t.c. in case you need a small touch of colour contrast. These colours cannot replace main colour palette or logotype official colours.

8

Brand Identity Guidelines Logo Usage

LOGOTYPE PRINT minimum size, 6 cm X 1,2 cm
LOGOTYPE SCREEN minimum size, 310 px X 51px

Clear space

The Clear Space zone around the logo has been determined to ensure the proper visibility of the HEADSTART logotype. Maintaining the Clear Space zone between the logo and other graphical elements such as typefaces, images, other logos, etc. ensures that the HEADSTART logo always appears unobstructed and distinctly separate from any other visuals.

Print Size 6 cm X 1,2 cm

Screen size 310 px X 51px

Minimum size

The Minimum size has been carefully determined to ensure that the HEADSTART logo is reproduced correctly in smaller sizes. At Minimum size, the logo is still clearly legible and easily identifiable. When using a lower quality printing technique (i.e. screenprinting), the usage of the logo in a larger size is strongly recommended.

9

Brand Identity Guidelines Logo Usage on Social Media

Logo use on social media: the logo should be used in a white background.

Twitter icon

FB icon

10

When placing the logo on an image, colour or pattern, it is essential that there is enough contrast between the logo and the background. The logo must not be placed on backgrounds that distract from or compete with the logo.

11

Display the HEADSTART logo only in the forms specified in this guide. The HEADSTART logo may not appear in any colour. Do not rotate, skew, scale, redraw, reproduce, alter or distort the HEADSTART logo in any way. Do not combine the HEADSTART logo with any other element such as other logos, words, graphics, photos, slogans or symbols.

12

HEADSTART Templates
PPT template (indicative slides)

Click to add title

✓ Topic 1

- This is the line for sub-section 1.1 (Use "tab" to create sub-section)
 - This is the line for sub-section 1.1.1 (Use "tab" to create sub-section)

✓ To activate a section of the outline:

- Highlight the section with a frame colored with RGB 114|191|68.
- Drag and drop the green frame; change height of frame if needed.

✓ If you want more slides of this type just choose the original slide in the preview window and press "ctrl" + "m".

Deliverable template (cover page)

Harmonised European Solutions for Testing Automation Road Transport

HEADSTART D.x. Deliverable title

Work package	WPx: Name of WP
Task	Task x.x: Name of task
Deliverable Lead	Partner Short name
Authors	Name (Company), Name (Company), Name (Company), Name (Company), Name (Company),
Dissemination level	Confidential (CO)
Status	Draft
Due date	00/00/2019
Document date	20/06/2019
Version number	x.x
<p><i>This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 824309.</i></p>	

PARTNERS

Disclaimer:

Content reflects only the authors' view and European Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

Minutes template

WP6 MEETING MINUTES

Workpackage	WP6
Meeting/telco	
Date	

List of participants

List of participants	
Partner	Name

Agenda

- Xxxxxxx
- xxxxxxx

Discussion

1. xxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxxx

Action List

Action Points

No.	Action	Responsible	Deadline	Status
1.				
2.				
3.				
4.				

Additional information

- The **next telco** will be on **xx/xx at xx:xx**
- The minutes will be available in the box, here:

- HEADSTART'S website: <https://www.headstart-project.eu/>
- HEADSTART'S email: info@headstart-project.com
- HEADSTART'S social media:
 - Twitter: [@HEADSTART_EU](https://twitter.com/HEADSTART_EU)
 - Facebook: [@HeadstartEUproject](https://www.facebook.com/HeadstartEUproject)
 - LinkedIn page: [HEADSTART-PROJECT](https://www.linkedin.com/company/HEADSTART-PROJECT)
 - LinkedIn group: [HEADSTART project](https://www.linkedin.com/groups/HEADSTART-project)

Press Activities

1st Press Release

PRESS RELEASE

The HEADSTART project (Harmonised European Solutions for Testing Automated Road Transport), launched its activities in the kick-off meeting in Brussels

The HEADSTART kickoff meeting was held in Brussels, Belgium on 23 & 24 January 2019. All the 17 partners, coming from 9 different EU countries had the opportunity to define together the mission and operational plan of the HEADSTART project.

HEADSTART, the new EU project which will run over the next three years aims to define testing and validation procedures on specific functionalities of Connected and Automated Driving (CAD). In more details HEADSTART will:

- Create a dynamic catalogue of existing methodologies, procedures, tools for testing and validation, taking into consideration the key groups requirements;
- Harmonise the existing testing and validation methodologies;
- Define and develop testing and validation methodologies for Connected and Automated Driving' functionalities building upon existing initiatives;
- Demonstrate the developed methodologies, procedures and tools through the testing of 4 specific CAD use cases;
- Reach consensus by creating and managing an expert network of CAD testing.

The kick-off meeting was organized to launch the beginning of the project and streamline the initial action plan. All the 8 Work Package Leaders had the opportunity to highlight the project goals, present their roles, responsibilities and plans towards the goals' accomplishment. The main goal of the meeting was to go-through

the project as well as to plan the project activities for the first six months. Tom Alkim, the European Commission Policy Officer and George Sarros, the Project Officer, presented the policy perspective and European Commission's expectations.

Editor Notes

Duration: 36 Months (January 1, 2019 – December 31, 2021)

EU contribution: 5,999.028.75 €

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 824309.

Coordinator: Mr. Álvaro Arrúe, Project Manager, IDIADA, Alvaro.Arrue@idiada.com

Partners:

The 17 partners are the following:

1. [IDIADA AUTOMOTIVE TECHNOLOGY SA](#), Spain
2. [INSTITUTE OF COMMUNICATION AND COMPUTER SYSTEMS](#), Greece
3. [4ACTIVESYSTEMS GMBH](#), Austria
4. [BUNDESANSTALT FUER STRASSENWESEN](#), Germany
5. [CENTRO RICERCHЕ FIAT SCPA](#), Italy
6. [EUROPEAN ROAD TRANSPORT TELEMATICS IMPLEMENTATION COORDINATION ORGANISATION - INTELLIGENT TRANSPORT SYSTEMS & SERVICES EUROPE](#), Belgium
7. [RHEINISCH-WESTFAELISCHE TECHNISCHE HOCHSCHULE AACHEN](#), Germany
8. [PILDO CONSULTING SL](#), Spain
9. [DIENST WEGVERKEER \(RDW\)](#), Netherlands
10. [SAFER](#), Sweden
11. [NEDERLANDSE ORGANISATIE VOOR TOEGEPAST NATUURWETENSCHAPPELIJK ONDERZOEK TNO](#), Netherlands
12. [VALEO VISION SAS](#), France
13. [FONDATION PARTENARIAL MOV'EOTEC](#), France
14. [FUNDACION CENTRO DE TECNOLOGIAS DE INTERACCION VISUAL Y COMUNICACIONES VICOMTECH](#), Spain

15. [Kompetenzzentrum – Das Virtuelle Fahrzeug-Forschungsgesellschaft mbH](#), Austria
16. [IVECO S.p.A.](#), Italy
17. [TOYOTA MOTOR EUROPE NV](#), Belgium

For more information:

Email: info@headstart-project.eu

Website: www.headstart-project.eu

Join us on social media: Facebook: [@HEADSTARTEUproject](#)
Twitter: [@HEADSTART_EU](#)
Linkedin: [HEADSTART -PROJECT](#)

HEADSTART Communication kit General Presentation

HARMONISED EUROPEAN SOLUTIONS
FOR TESTING AUTOMATED ROAD TRANSPORT

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 824309.

Outline

- ✓ HEADSTART project facts
- ✓ HEADSTART Consortium
- ✓ Overview
- ✓ Project's concept
- ✓ Project's objectives
- ✓ Work Package Structure
- ✓ Test sites
- ✓ Expected Technical Results up to M12
- ✓ Expected impact
- ✓ Cooperate with HEADSTART project
- ✓ HEADSTART Partners
- ✓ Stay connected with HEADSTART

HEADSTART project facts

- ✓ **Call identifier:** ART-01-2018
- ✓ **Type:** RIA
- ✓ **Duration:** 01.2019 – 12.2021 (36 months)
- ✓ **Budget:** 6M€
- ✓ **Consortium:** 17 partners
- ✓ **Coordinator:** Applus IDIADA, Mr. Álvaro Arrue, Project Manager
- ✓ **Dissemination Manager:** ICCS, Dr. Angelos Amditis, Research Director
- ✓ **Website:** <https://www.headstart-project.eu>
- ✓ **Social media:** / HEADSTART_EU
 - in / HEADSTART-PROJECT
 - in / HEADSTART project (Group)
 - f / @HeadstartEUproject

HEADSTART Consortium

Overview

The **HEADSTART** project:

- ✓ aims to define testing and validation procedures of Connected and Automated Driving functions including key technologies such as communications, cyber-security and positioning;
- ✓ will execute tests which will be in both simulation and real-world fields to validate safety and security performance according to the key users' needs;
- ✓ will bring together the consortium with other European and national CAD stakeholders to cluster the most relevant existing initiatives, develop methodologies, procedures and tools and drive in a harmonized European solution for testing and validation of automated road vehicles;
- ✓ will address relevant stakeholders to join the experts' network so as to configure together the methodologies used and also promote the project results' adoption.

20/6/2019

Event/venue

5

Project's Concept

- | | |
|---|--|
| <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ① Integration of positioning, communications and cyber-security in CAD test scenarios ② Comprehensive procedure for the allocation of test cases per testing platform ③ Selection criteria and specification for proving ground test scenarios taking into account criticality ④ Proving ground testing and evaluation | <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ⑤ Correlation between simulation and proving ground results ⑥ Harmonised, open result compilation and sharing ⑦ Field trial test methodology description ⑧ Cyber-security principles and integration in the testing methodology |
|---|--|

20/6/2019

Event/venue

6

Project's Objectives

HEADSTART will define testing and validation procedures of CAD functions including:

- its key enabling technologies (i.e. communication, cyber-security, positioning)
- by cross-linking of all test instances such as simulation, proving ground and real world field tests
- to validate safety and security performance according to the needs of key user groups (technology developers, consumer testing and type approval)

20/6/2019

Event/venue

7

Work Package Structure

20/6/2019

Event/venue

8

Test sites

IDIADA test site, Spain

LELYSTADT test site, the Netherlands

Aldehnoven test site, Germany

AstaZero test site, Sweden

DITCM test site, the Netherlands

20/6/2019

Event/venue

9

Expected Technical Results up to M12

List of Deliverables M1 – M12

Del. No.	Deliverable Title	Lead Beneficiary	Due Date	Rev1	Rev2
D1.1	State of innovation of existing initiatives and gap analysis	IKA	M6	TNO	TNO
D1.2	Stakeholders and user group needs	VEDECOM	M6	IDI	ERTICO
D1.3	Technical and functional requirements for KETs	SAFER	M9	VICOMTE CH	IVECO
D1.4	Functional requirements of selected use cases	SAFER	M9	VIF	ika
D2.1	Common methodology for test, validation and certification	IKA	M12	BASt	RDW

20/6/2019

Event/venue

10

Expected Impact

✓ Testing and validation

- End users: OEMs, Tier1, tools providers

✓ Assessment (Consumer Testing)

- End users: Euro NCAP

✓ Certification (type approval)

- End users: Type approval authorities & Technical services

20/6/2019

Event/venue

11

Cooperate with HEADSTART project

EXPERT GROUP PARTICIPATION

- Join as associated partner and our expert group
- Join the discussion group of your interest:
 - Cyber-security
 - Communications (V2X)
 - Positioning
 - Scenario selection
 - Consumer testing (NCAP)
 - Type approval
- Provide needs and requirements and evaluate project (intermediate) results

JOINT TESTING ACTION

- ✓ Joint cooperation between both projects for testing validation and certification purposes
- ✓ Align your project with the harmonized methodology and tools developed within HEADSTART
- ✓ Become one of our use cases!

Please let us know about your interest and join our distribution list.

Website: www.headstart-project.eu

Contact: info@headstart-project.eu

20/6/2019

Event/venue

12

 HEADSTART

HEADSTART Partners

20/6/2019 Event/venue 13

 HEADSTART

Stay connected with HEADSTART

- ✓ Visit HEADSTART website
www.headstart-project.eu
- ✓ Follow our Social Media:
 - [@HEADSTART_EU](https://twitter.com/HEADSTART_EU)
 - HEADSTART-PROJECT
 - HEADSTART project (Group)
 - @HeadstartEUproject
- ✓ Reach us via an e-mail:
info@headstart-project.eu
- ✓ Sign up to our newsletter:
<https://lists.iccs.gr/wws/subscribe/headstart-news>
- ✓ Get in touch with our partners

20/6/2019 Event/venue 14

Thank you!

Any questions?

Name of presenter

Job title affiliation

Contact details

(4 lines max)

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 824309.

Annex 2: Dissemination procedures

Description and purpose¶

The participation of any Partner in an event as well as the performance of every dissemination activity related to the HEADSTART project has to be **approved beforehand by the HEADSTART project Coordinator and the project Steering Committee (SC)**.

Basic objective:

- Produce high quality HEADSTART publications and presentations;
- Avoid overlaps and possible disclosure of restricted or confidential information;
- Monitoring and record the dissemination activities of the project in a sufficient way.

Step by step procedure:

1. Fill in the spaces of the table below;
2. Store your material (abstract, draft paper, poster etc.) to the BOX online repository (link);
3. Submit your dissemination request providing **for minimum two weeks before submission** deadline by email to the WP6 Leader ([Mrs. Nikoletta Karitsioti](mailto:Mrs.Nikoletta.Karitsioti), nikoletta.karitsioti@iccs.gr);
4. WP6 Leader has 2 days to react and send the request to Coordinator/SC for approval, modification or rejection;
5. Coordinator/SC decision send to the WP6 Leader **within five working days**; If no answer is received due to the set deadline it is taken as an approval;
6. WP6 Leader informs the involved partner(s) about the decision.

In case of:

A) **Approval**: When approval is given through the WP6 Leader the partner(s) are free to proceed with the realisation of the proposed dissemination activity;

B) **Conflict/objection**: Any SC member can reject the proposed dissemination activity if they have objections, related to overlaps or possible disclosure of restricted or confidential information concern the work performed in the different WPs. In case of conflict, the issue is being discussed among the coordinator, the WP6 Leader and the involved partners;

**If a conflict is created or further material is needed then WP6 Leader informs the partner and requires modifications or additions. Then the material is proposed again to WP6 Leader and if significant changes that might provoke conflicts among partners' interests must be made, the previous procedure is followed.

- **Dissemination activities report**: Within **ten working days** after the realisation of the approved dissemination activity, the partner should provide the WP6 Leader (nikoletta.karitsioti@iccs.gr) with the filled in dissemination report and the presented dissemination material (final paper, presentation, poster etc.). The dissemination report form is stored in the BOX online repository (link). All material will be archived by ICCS to the BOX online repository (link).

NOTE:

- If partners wish to present or release material already approved as public presentation and material then no formal approval is required. The WP6 Leader (nikoletta.karitsioti@iccs.gr;) has to be informed. If there are no objections, then the WP6 Leader notifies the authors to proceed with the dissemination activity.
- In case a partner wishes to organise a workshop or special event related to HEADSTART, then the approval of WP6 Leader and the information of the Coordinator and the SC is also needed **2 months** before the realisation of this dissemination activity.

Non-European Travel

** For non-European travels the PO should be informed and an approval from his side is required. Please fill-in the **Non-European Travel Report Template** (<https://app.box.com/folder/68782237522>) at least **two months** before the travel and send the form to the project Coordinator (Alvaro.Arrue@idiada.com), so as to inform the EC. For possible enquiry by the auditors in the future it is recommended to keep the form and EC's response with the respective travel documents.

Acknowledgement

The following acknowledgement text should be included in all publications related to the HEADSTART work:

“This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 824309. Content reflects only the authors’ view and European Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.”

For other communication activities, the EC emblem with the phrase:

“This work is a part of the HEADSTART project. This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 824309”

For infrastructure, equipment & major results, the EC emblem & the phrase:

“This [infrastructure][equipment][insert type of result] is part of HEADSTART project that has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 824309”

For correct use of the EC emblem please use the following link:

- European flag:

http://europa.eu/about-eu/basic-information/symbols/flag/index_en.htm

For further information please contact the WP6 Leader (nikoletta.karitsioti@iccs.gr;))

Dissemination Requests Table

No.	Date of dissemination request	Main Leader	Type of activity	Title of the event/journal	Date and location	URL/website	Title of publication/presentation	Abstract	Authors	Relation to HEADSTART	BOX link to document
-----	-------------------------------	-------------	------------------	----------------------------	-------------------	-------------	-----------------------------------	----------	---------	-----------------------	----------------------

No.	Date of dissemination request	Main Leader	Type of activity	Title of the event/journal	Date and location	URL/website	Title of publication/presentation	Abstract	Authors	Relation to HEADSTART	BOX link to document

HEADSTART Dissemination Activities Report

This form is established to serve two purposes:

1. to keep a record on the HEADSTART representations on external events;
2. to collect input for a news item on the HEADSTART knowledge platform and other dissemination activities.

In case that a partner has participated in the event in multiple capacities/roles, please fill out this form on the capacity as HEADSTART partner.

After filling in the form, please send to nikoletta.karitsioti@iccs.gr, including partners or other supporting documents (e.g. quotes, presentation, photos e.t.c.) if any.

You may find below three report forms:

- In case of event
- In case of scientific publication
- In case of other activities

Report form in case of events

Name:	
Organization:	
Type of activity:	conference, workshop, meeting e.t.c.
Title of event:	
Location:	city, country
Date(s):	
Organizer(s):	
Was HEADSTART invited to attend?	

Relation to HEADSTART:	
Topic:	
Size of event:	number of participants
Kind of audience:	e.g. scientists, policymakers, media e.t.c.
URL/Website:	
Setup of the event	Formal, interactive, plenary sessions e.t.c.
Partner's role in the event	Speaker/ panel member/ co-organizer e.t.c.
Other HEADSTART partners	
Size of audience	(approximate number)
Keynote speaker(s)	
Relevant to HEADSTART sessions of significance	
Outcomes of the event	
Opportunities/ implications identified for HEADSTART	
<p>1. Can this information be put online on the HEADSTART website? (tick box)</p> <p>a. Yes</p>	

b. No, it is confidential / for internal use only.
<p>2. Can this information be put online on the HEADSTART newsletter? (tick box)</p> <p>a. Yes</p> <p>b. No, it is confidential / for internal use only</p>

Report form in case of Scientific Publication
(Conference papers, journals / magazines, book chapter e.t.c.)

Type of publication	Journal, article, paper e.t.c.	
Main Author (name, organisation)		
Title of publication:		
Relevance to HEADSTART:	Please specify: WPx work, concept description e.t.c.	
Other Authors:		
In case of a journal/magazine article:	Title of journal or magazine:	
	Volume, page:	
	Editor / Publisher:	
	ISSN:	

In case of a Conference paper:	Title of proceedings	
	Editor/publisher:	
In case of a book publication:	Title of book:	
	Title of Chapter:	
	Editor / Publisher:	
	Pages:	
	ISBN:	
For all publications:	Date of publication:	
	URL (if available)	
	DOI number	
	Open access to publication?	<input type="checkbox"/> no <input type="checkbox"/> yes: (way to get it)
	Additional info:	

Report form in case of other dissemination activities

Type of activity:	i.e. video presentation, event organization, website announcement, press briefings, interviews e.t.c.
Title:	
Occasion:	Name of event/publication/video e.t.c.
URL:	
Relevance to HEADSTART:	
Partners involved:	
Short description:	
Other comments:	
<p>1. Can this information be put online on the HEADSTART website? (tick box)</p> <p>a. Yes</p> <p>b. No, it is confidential / for internal use only.</p>	
<p>2. Can this information be put online on the HEADSTART newsletter? (tick box)</p> <p>a. Yes</p> <p>b. No, it is confidential / for internal use only.</p>	

Report on Non-European Travel

Please fill-in before the travel and send the form to the project coordinator (Alvaro.Arrue@idiada.com);, so as to inform the EC. For possible enquiry by the auditors in the future it is recommended to keep the form and EC's response with the respective travel documents.

Partner's Name	
Name of traveller(s)	
E-mail of traveller(s)	
Date, place & title of event (including URL)	
Estimated costs (Flight, hotel, subsistence)	
	Justification (Please name the reason and your motivation for the travel. Describe how the HEADSTART work will be supported and benefited from this travel.)

Annex 3: HEADSTART indicative list of proposed events

Date	Event	Location	Website
July 15-18, 2019	Automated Vehicle Symposium	Orlando, Florida, USA	Orlando World Center Marriott, 8701 World Center Dr, Orlando, FL 32821, USA
August, 2019	Maven	N/A	
September, 2019	ERTICO Think Tank	N/A	
September, 2019	ARCADE- Concertation meeting ad-hoc	N/A	
September, 2019	Vi-DAS	N/A	http://www.vi-das.eu/
September, 2019	ADAS&ME	N/A	http://www.adasandme.com/
October 14-17, 2019	Road Safety and Simulation International Conference (RSS)	Iowa City, Iowa, USA	https://rss2019.org/
October 16-17, 2019	Autonomy (Paris)	Paris, France	https://www.autonomy.paris/en/
October 21-25, 2019	ITS World Congress	Singapore	https://itsworldcongress2019.com/
October 27-30, 2019	IEEE Intelligent Transportation Systems Conference (ITSC)	Auckland, New Zealand	https://www.itsc2019.org/
October, 2019	Euro NCAP - Test campaigns	N/A	N/A
November 12-14, 2019	sip-ADUS	Tokyo, Japan	http://en.sip-adus.go.jp/
November 2019	EUCAR conference	N/A	N/A

Date	Event	Location	Website
January 12-16, 2020	Transportation Research Board (TRB) Annual Meeting	Washington, USA	http://www.trb.org/AnnualMeeting/AnnualMeeting.aspx
April 27-30, 2020	TRA Symposium	Messukeskus Helsinki	https://traconference.eu/
September 14-18, 2020	FISITA World Automotive Congress	Prague, Czech Republic	https://www.fisita.com/fisita2020

Harmonised European Solutions for Testing Automation Road Transport

Disclaimer:

Content reflects only the authors' view and European Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.